

AN APPROACH TOWARDS A BASIC MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION FOR THE SIMULATION OF PROCESS INDUCED DEFORMATIONS

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Abstract

Economic considerations in terms of productivity and the optimal utilization of the properties of composite structures increasingly demand highly integrated structures. The associated rise in geometric complexity in conjunction with consistently high tolerance requirements, especially in the aerospace sector, face both the tool designer and the process engineer with the challenge to design the tool geometry as well as the manufacturing process in a way to achieve a deformation neutral component "first right". Finite element based simulation tools are more and more used to virtually process the part and analyze residual stress and deformation a priori. Detailed modeling of various thermo-chemical and physical phenomena requires correspondent high characterization effort. In the work at hand the results of a small number of characterization tests together with literature data and virtual testing were assembled in a basic material characterization and subsequently used for the simulation of a generic validation structure with the commercial software program Compro. A comparison between simulated and experimentally determined spring-in angle indicated a good applicability of the parameter set under standard processing conditions for the configuration of concern.

1 Introduction

Residual deformations arising out of the manufacturing process for structures made up of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) present two challenges for the design engineer: deficient dimensional fidelity may compromise components function and/or rigging forces required to mount the component in the system exceed allowable limits. In the latter case rework of part features or even expensive tooling adaption and potential part rejection is a risk to be investigated thoroughly. Whether or not part geometrical deviations as-built present a problem is subject to the effect of component loss (cost) and tooling rework effort opposed to the uncertainty in a priori knowledge on projected deformations [1]. Besides the individual industrial experience on expected deformations for similar setups and the trial and error approach, tools to estimate residual deformations are available ranging from simple analytical approaches ([2], [3]) over intermediate phenomenological simulation [4] to detailed process modeling and simulation ([5], [6], [7]). Detailed methods aim to capture underlying physics via modeling the cure dependent thermal and mechanical response of the structure. In addition to estimating the residual stress and deformation

they present a platform for virtual testing and boost understanding of the full manufacturing process. A drawback is the extensive materials characterization required to feed various property development models.

Process induced deformations (PID) can be classified in three categories: material imbalance, stress gradients and strain anisotropy [8]. Examples for material imbalance are fiber volume fraction gradients or, in the most obvious case, asymmetric ply stacking sequences. For modern "no bleed" systems the effect of resulting material asymmetry due to resin bleed usually can be neglected and symmetric ply layups are general practice in industry.

The relevance of the stress transfer from the tool to the part during the heat up phase of a typical autoclave cure is strongly dependent on process, setup and part geometry related boundary conditions. Detailed methods to capture the effect of tool part interaction require the calibration of an appropriate interface model to the particular setup ([9], [10], [11]) and cannot be generalized.

However, the distinct orthotropic nature of CFRP material with a high modulus and low straining during processing in fiber direction and a

low modulus combined with comparably high thermal and cure shrinkage strains in the fiber transverse direction leads to strain incompatibilities on different length scales. The effect of the incompatibility between in-plane and through-thickness strains in curved part features is commonly known as “spring-in”. Anisotropic thermal and cure shrinkage strains are a major factor of influence on PID [7].

In order to account for the relevant drivers during processing in terms of strain anisotropy, thermo-chemical and mechanical properties of the constituents of the composite material are needed, namely the cure rate (cure kinetics), thermal conductivity and specific heat, phase transitions (gelation, glass transition), volumetric cure shrinkage and modulus development of the matrix, as well as thermal and mechanical properties of the fibers, which are reported to be relatively constant during processing [5], [6].

In the following, an approach is outlined to estimate the parameters for the essential elements in process simulation listed above based on a minimal set of dynamic scanning calorimetry (DSC) and rheometer tests.

2 Characterization of Resin Property Development Models

2.1 Thermo-chemical Properties, Transition between Morphological Phases

In order to solve the heat conduction problem, (directional) heat conductivities, specific heat capacities and densities needs to be known for all materials within the manufacturing setup. Moreover the crosslinking reaction of the thermoset resin in terms of energy release as well as parameters describing the phase transitions need to be defined.

2.1.1 Cure Kinetics

Phenomenological or semi-empirical cure kinetics models describing the cure rate as a function of the current degree of cure, the temperature and additional variables to describe the diffusion controlled regime are commonly utilized to model the progress of cure (e.g. [8]). For all phenomenological models the heat flow into a resin sample is evaluated employing dynamic scanning calorimetry (DSC). The central assumption

facilitating the evaluation the experimental data is that the instantaneous heat flow into the sample \dot{H} equals the change in the degree of conversion α :

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{\dot{H}}{\Delta H_{total}} \quad (1)$$

The total heat of reaction ΔH_{total} has been determined as the integrated heat flow from dynamic DSC scans at a heating rate of 10 K/min with a value of 457.15 (J/g) for the resin system of concern, Hexcel M18/1 with a sample standard deviation of 6.43 (J/g).

Dynamical and isothermal runs are reported to be used for the model fit as the experimental data basis, e.g. [12]. Isothermal runs have been used here for the calibration of the kinetics model constants for several reasons: on the one hand cure cycles for autoclave cured high performance aerospace resins are designed such that gelation takes place during the second hold and therefore the most relevant fraction of curing with regard to residual stress build up due to cure shrinkage strains occurs at a constant temperature. For isothermal runs on the other hand diffusion control plays a distinctive role and needs to be taken into account ([6], [8]).

For all DSC measurements, the lower value for the recommended sample mass of 5-20 mg according to ISO 11357 has been targeted to minimize sample thermal inertia and exotherm. Isothermal runs have been conducted with a maximum heating rate to equilibrate the temperature at a targeted value of 140°C, 160°C and 180°C. A horizontal baseline has been utilized to isolate the heat flow due to the crosslinking reaction (ISO 11357). Corruptive dynamic effects in the heat flow at the start of the experiments have been discarded from the data for the model fit, but still the released enthalpy was taken into account as an individual additional component of the initial degree of cure for each data set. Fig. 1 shows this occurrence exemplarily on an isothermal run at 160°C.

A MATLAB code has been generated to conduct a nonlinear regression analysis (Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm) for a least-squares model fit based on isothermal DSC data. Seven most established cure kinetics models have been implemented and the fit is generated sequentially for

all models, providing a summary on the individual model fits in a visual and numerical format. Available kinetics models are namely the autocatalytic and n^{th} order model, the autocatalytic n^{th} order model with and without modeling of the transition to the diffusion controlled regime, the model of Lee, Chun and Lin [13] and the model of Hubert and Johnston [14], [6]. A linear temperature dependency has been added to the exponents for all models similar to the way it is reported in [8] for the autocatalytic model of n^{th} order.

The amount of network formation in the prepreg material of concern in delivery state is unknown and has been taken into account via an initial degree of cure as suggested in [6]. A good fit of the model of Hubert and Johnston, called M7 here, with experimental heat flow data, was found with an initial degree of cure of 0.05. Model prediction and experimental data are shown for the cure rate and the degree of cure progression in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 respectively. The model parameters for the cure kinetics model are listed in Table 1 where T_c represents the cure temperature.

2.1.2 Gelation

The cure state when an infinite molecular network is established has two important aspects within the work at hand: on the one hand it is an input parameter for the process simulation software package of choice [15]. On the other hand it is a point to be identified easily with rheological tests and therefore can serve as a measure for the calibration of experimental data. The statement, that the resin degree of cure at gelation is a material constant can be supported by the work of [16] and is implicitly presumed in [6] and [14]. For the determination of the degree of cure at gelation gel times have been extracted out of the manufacturer data sheet [17] and the degree of cure has been calculated for every temperature based on the cure kinetics model presented above (cf. Fig. 4). The mean value for the degree of cure at gelation has been determined at 40.76% conversion with a sample standard deviation of 0.67%.

2.1.3 Glass Transition Temperature

After gelation and prior to vitrification relaxation times of the visco-elastic solid increase dramatically: the mechanical behavior is more and more dominated by the elastic component and

residual stresses build up due to the mismatch of thermal and cure shrinkage strains on micro level between fiber and matrix as well as on a macro scale between differently oriented plies generally referred to as the strain anisotropy [8]. The glass transition temperature describes the transition from a rubbery like to a glassy solid during a typical cure cycle for epoxy resins and is one of the most important parameters to describe the change in resin modulus ([6], [7]).

Usually the progression of the glass transition temperature with cure is quantified based on the T_g measurement for a series of neat resin samples at various degrees of cure which are fit to the Di Benedetto equation (e.g. [12]). This is not further elaborated here. Instead a virtual testing approach is proposed utilizing available data and a small set of dynamic DSC runs.

The relatively simple model projected to capture the development of the resin modulus during cure (cf. chapter 2.2.3) requires a linear function for the variation of T_g with the degree of cure. A linear model has also been utilized as one of the simplest approximations of the true progression elsewhere [7]. Given a linear dependency it is sufficient to determine the glass transition temperature at two points: for instance in the as-received state and an additional point where reliable data is at hand. The glass transition temperature in the as-received state of the resin material is relatively consistent, with a mean value of 0.31°C and a sample standard deviation of 0.88°C based on 5 dynamic DSC runs where the inflection point has been used as T_g according to ISO 11357-2.

For a standard cure cycle the glass transition temperature is given with a value of 196°C in the materials data sheet [17]. On a “0D” simulation conducted in Compro/Raven [15] based on the cure kinetics model described above and the manufacturer recommended cure cycle, the degree of cure at the end of the cycle is predicted to be 0.88. Taking into account the initial degree of cure defined for the cure kinetics model (chapter 2.1.1), the following variation of T_g with degree of cure was established:

$$T_g [^{\circ}\text{C}] = -11.47 + 235.67 \cdot \alpha \quad (2)$$

where α is the degree of cure.

2.1.4 Conductivities, Specific Heat, Density

Conductivity and specific heat of the resin system Hexcel M18/1 were estimated based on the respective values for fully cured Hexcel 3501-6 and 8552 (cf. Table 2). The mass density of the material of concern is given in [17] with a value of 1220 (g/cm³) assumed to be valid for fully cured neat resin at room temperature. No dependency of relevant quantities on temperature or degree of cure was taken into account. Based on the sensitivity study presented in [6] the effect of the uncertainty concerning accurate resin conductivity, specific heat and mass density characterization on the results of the process simulation in terms of residual deformations is assumed to be low.

2.2 Mechanical Properties

2.2.1 Experimental Setup and Measured Quantities

A rheometer (Anton Paar MCR 302) has been utilized to characterize resin properties during cure. The instrument was set up with a plate-plate specimen holder and operated in oscillation mode. The settings have been chosen according to the instrument's manufacturer recommendations for epoxy resins with a frequency of 1.59 Hz and a maximum deformation of 0.07%.

Resin film was applied to the specimen pan and heated in an oven at 75°C for 10 minutes. The rheometer was heated up to the test temperature for the isothermal runs, which has been defined as 160°C and 180°C. The pan with the liquid resin was applied in the test fixture and the gap between the pan and the slide was automatically adjusted to 1mm. After 3 minutes of temperature equilibration in the machine, the test program was started where the axial force was kept constant at nominal 0 N while in addition to the viscosity, storage and loss modulus readings also the gap distance was monitored. The latter was utilized to estimate the resin cure shrinkage evolution during cure.

According to ASTM D 4473 the point of gelation can be determined precisely in identifying the situation when the loss factor tan(δ) equals 1, which means that the storage modulus G' and the loss modulus G'' are equal. Fig. 5 exemplarily shows the experimental data generated on a 180°C isothermal run. The loss factor passes through the value 1 after approximately 580 seconds. Shortly after that resin cure shrinkage starts to progress as

the resin cannot replenish into the measurement gap anymore. Due to the high ratio between the diameter of the slide (25mm) and the gap width (1mm) the resin material in the gap is considered clamped in radial direction and the volumetric shrinkage is assumed to act completely in axial direction [18].

2.2.2 Resin Cure Shrinkage

Combining the degree of cure at gelation with the cure kinetics model for the isothermal cure, cure shrinkage (CS) and modulus progression can be projected on the degree of cure. The result for the cure shrinkage is shown in Fig. 6. A linear relationship between the volumetric cure shrinkage and the degree of cure is often employed ([7], [19]). When shifting the linear cure shrinkage model calibrated to the experimental data in order to comply with the initial degree of cure for the neat resin material (cf. chapter 2.1.1), a (theoretical) total volumetric cure shrinkage of approximately 8% is calculated for the resin system Hexcel M18/1.

2.2.3 Modulus Development

During a dynamic rheometer run also the complex shear modulus and its components storage and loss modulus are gauged. Reliability on absolute values of modulus readings on a rheometer are generally low as the measured torsion moment spans 6 to 7 orders of magnitude and the rheometer as such is designed to reflect rheology appropriately, which implies the emphasis of accuracy for small loads. However not the absolute values of the modulus are of interest but solely the progression as a function of degree of cure and temperature in order to calibrate a simple modulus development model. The model which has been chosen is model 2 of the work of A. Johnston [6]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_r' &= E_r^0 && \text{for } T^* < T_{C1}^* && (3) \\
 E_r' &= E_r^0 + \frac{T^* - T_{C1}^*}{T_{C2}^* - T_{C1}^*} \cdot (E_r^\infty - E_r^0) && \text{for } T_{C1}^* < T^* < T_{C2}^* \\
 E_r' &= E_r^\infty && \text{for } T^* > T_{C2}^* \\
 E_r &= E_r' \cdot [1 + a_{Er} \cdot (T - T_0)] \\
 \text{where: } T^* &= (T_{ga} + T_{gb} \cdot \alpha) - T; \quad T_{C1}^* = T_{C1a}^* + T_{C1b}^* \cdot T
 \end{aligned}$$

For a description of the model parameters see Table 3. One of the core assumptions in the approach to modeling the progression of the mechanical properties of the resin is a constant bulk modulus throughout processing [5]. Given the mechanical properties of the resin of concern in the

fully cured state, the knowledge of the initiation and completion of the development of the Young's Modulus *or* the shear modulus in terms of state variables is sufficient for estimating the mechanical properties of the resin during cure.

Fig. 7 shows the measured progression of G' versus the degree of cure for two temperature levels tested. Degree of cure at vitrification has been calculated based on data presented above at 0.73 for an isothermal cure at 160°C and 0.81 at 180°C respectively. In addition to the modulus also the critical temperature T^* , which represents the difference between the instantaneous glass transition temperature and the cure temperature, is plotted as a function of the degree of cure. A best-fit line has been generated for the relevant linear section of the G' progression as indicated exemplarily with a dashed line in Fig. 7. The value at the intersection with the x-axis is used as an approximation for the initiation of modulus development quantified with T_{C1}^* . The lower critical degree of cure has been determined to be approximately 0.65 for isothermal cure at 160°C and 0.71 for 180°C respectively. Out of this information the parameters for the variation of the lower critical temperature T_{C1}^* with temperature have been determined. The upper critical temperature T_{C2}^* where the full modulus is achieved needs to be constant within the model of choice. A value of $T_{C2}^* = -9K$ has been picked as it presents a good compromise on plateau accomplishment for the 180°C samples, which are regarded as more relevant for a 180°C curing resin system. The plateau value for the modulus after cure E_r^∞ has been taken out of the manufacturer's data sheet [17], and the initial resin modulus has been arbitrarily chosen to $E_r^\infty / 1000$. All relevant parameters describing the resin's mechanical behavior during cure are depicted in table 3.

2.2.4 Coefficient of Thermal Expansion

Residual deformations due to the mismatch of thermal strains in the laminate during processing substantially contribute to the global distortion of a CFRP part after de-molding. The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) in the gelled state is reported to amount 2.5 times the value in the glassy state [7]. Based on this assumption and a CTE of the resin of 55 ($\mu\text{m}/\text{mK}$) in the fully cured state at room temperature [17], the progression of the matrix CTE during cure can be modeled with a transition from a

value of 137.5 [$\mu\text{m}/\text{mK}$] to 55 [$\mu\text{m}/\text{mK}$] as the resin vitrifies during cure and changes from the gelled to the glassy state. The CTE progression with degree of cure is shown for a typical cure cycle in Fig. 8.

3 Fiber Properties

Fiber properties for the carbon type AS4C which are used in HexPly© M18/1 are assumed to be equal to those of AS4. Thermal and mechanical properties of AS4 fibers can be found in [6] and [20]. Orthotropic expansion and heat conductivity coefficients as well as specific heat capacity for the fiber material have been used according to [6] as extensive experimental data is presented in the mentioned source generated for a similar prepreg system.

Fiber transversely isotropic mechanical properties have been defined as constant over processing. As resulting ply properties calculated based on the micromechanics model [5] in conjunction with the resin modulus in fully cured state resulted in a better match with fiber mechanical properties based on [20], the latter source has been used.

Table 4 summarizes fiber thermal and mechanical properties.

4 Validation

4.1 Experimental Spring-In Data

L-shaped monolithic specimens with a symmetric layout and a 90° angle between the two flanges have been manufactured on an aluminum tool according to the aerospace specifications. The samples have a radius of 35mm, the flanges have a span wise length of 185mm and a width of 190mm. The layout consists of 16 plies and is a mixture of woven fabric reinforced M18/1 and unidirectional plies (Fig. 9).

Prior to layout the tool has been coated with a spray release agent. Intermediate debulking during layout allowed to achieve a laminate quality similar to the serial production process. Thermo sensors were applied at the bottom and top surfaces of the laminate at the edges of the profiles for the lead/lag control of the research autoclave the samples were built in.

After curing and removing the part from the tool, the actual geometry has been determined using a coordinate measurement machine (CMM). A grid of circles to serve as indicators for the measurement points was projected on the part during cure as the negative of closed slots milled into the tool. Fig. 10 shows the grid of measurement points as well as axial positions organizing respective CMM points in sections on a CAD representation of the sample.

Only the effect of the strain anisotropy resulting in spring-in – referred to as “pure” spring-in here – is of interest for the validation of the material property development models. For this reason the spring-in at the transition between the radius and the flange has been evaluated. Spring-in angle has been calculated as the difference between the original angle and the angle between lines through points at the radius-flange transition and the adjacent measurement point. It is understood that the effect of warpage due to tool part interaction at the radius in tangential direction is neglected assuming the spring-in value derived in the described manner as purely due to strain anisotropy.

The values for the 5 positions in axial direction are shown in Fig. 11. Spring-in values have consistently a minimum at the mid position and a maximum at the edges in axial direction. This fact is attributed to the effect of tool part interaction and the stress transfer from the tool to the part during heat up in longitudinal direction. In order to minimize the effect only values at the mid position (position P3) are taken into account. The mean value at this location amounts 1.187° with a sample standard deviation of 0.047° .

4.2 Compro2D Simulation

All property development models introduced above have been incorporated in a material card for the commercial process simulation tool Compro [15]. Additionally, a FE description has been generated. Thermal boundary conditions have been chosen in a way, that on top and bottom of the laminate experimental thermo sensor readings and nodal temperatures are in reasonable agreement. Fig. 12 shows the simulated temperatures in comparison with the temperature signal of the thermocouple “TE7”. Due to the lack of the tool and the thermal mass associated with it, an artificial temperature overshoot is apparent. As the

temperature difference between tool side and bag side is minimal no significant effect in terms of cure gradients is expected.

The geometric boundary condition on the part imposed by the tool has been modeled as a sliding boundary condition at the tool side of the part so the part cannot penetrate the virtual tool. The results of the process simulation for the L-shaped angle show a residual spring-in of 1.156° after tool removal (cf. Fig. 13). This is in good agreement with the mean value of the “pure” spring-in isolated from experimental CMM data.

5 Discussion

Extensive materials characterization effort is necessary to parameterize various property development models utilizing detailed methods for the determination of process induced deformations. In the work at hand a basic materials characterization has been generated combining a minimal data set of DSC and rheometer runs, virtual testing and the utilization of relevant publically available information for the constituents of the prepreg material of concern. A comparison of experimentally determined spring-in angle with the results of a Compro [15] simulation based on generated materials data for an L-shaped profile has been used as a validation of the approach. The difference between the simulated and measured value for the corner component of the spring-in is less than 3%.

The property development models calibrated as part of the work have been shown to deliver good results for PID due to strain anisotropy for a relatively thin laminate cured with the standard cure cycle. Processing of aerospace grade materials underlies stringent specifications leading to a small process window. However the effect of uncertainty especially of the estimated T_g progression, which drives initiation of residual stress build up due to strain mismatch on lamina and laminate level, should be checked for deviations from the manufacturer recommended cure cycle (MRCC) in terms of heating rates and hold times. Single isothermal DSC runs have been utilized to parameterize the cure kinetics model of choice. Repetitions of the runs with additional temperature levels in conjunction with DSC runs of variations of the MRCC would present a basis to quantify the

uncertainty in the progression of the degree of cure and serve as a basis for subsequent evaluation of the effect on simulated deformations. Applicability of the property development models for the determination of warpage due to cure gradients relevant on thick parts and/or setups with low conductivity tooling materials should be tested.

The initial resin modulus is driving the stress gradient due to tool part interaction (TPI) at low degrees of cure in the heat up phase of the cure cycle responsible for the concerning warpage component [21]. An interface model utilizing the resin modulus development model based on an arbitrarily chosen initial value could be calibrated to fit experimentally determined warpage measures. However the stress distribution in the laminate cannot be accurately captured.

In general the results of process simulations using a detailed characterization of the material should be conducted for a range of processing conditions and opposed with the results based on the basic characterization and respective experimental data. In this way the range of applicability for the material characterization shown can be identified and serve as a basis to evaluate the trade-off between characterization effort, versatility and accuracy.

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Fig. 1. Dynamic effects at the start of the reaction treated as a component of the initial degree of cure for the model fit

Fig. 2. Experimental data and model fit for the isothermal cure rate at 140°C, 160°C and 180°C

Fig. 3. Experimental data and model fit for the degree of cure during isothermal cure at 140°C, 160°C and 180°C

Fig. 4. Gel times [17] and corresponding degree of cure based on calibrated cure kinetics model

Fig. 5. Experimental modulus and cure shrinkage data for an isothermal rheometer run at 180°C

Fig. 6. Experimental cure shrinkage data projected on degree of cure progression after gelation and deduced linear model

Fig. 7. Progression of the storage modulus G' and the critical temperature T^* versus degree of cure for isothermal rheometer runs at 160°C and 180°C (sample indication "S1" to "S5")

Fig. 8. Matrix CTE versus degree of cure after gelation for a typical cure cycle

Fig. 9. Schematic of test specimen layout

Fig. 10. CAD representation of test sample with grid of CMM points and axial positions P1 to P5

Fig. 13. Deformed plot out of Compro/Raven simulation of L-shaped specimen, deformation scale factor: 5

Fig. 11. Mean values of measured spring-in corner component at axial measurement positions

Table 1. Parameters of calibrated cure kinetics model

	<i>A</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>α_{CT}</i>	<i>α_{C0}</i>
	(1/s)	(J/mol)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(1/K)	(-)
Cure kinetics model "M7" ([14],[6])							
$\frac{k \cdot \alpha^m \cdot (1-\alpha)^n}{1 + e^{C(\alpha - \alpha_{CT} + \alpha_{CT} T_C)}}$	4.512E+04	5.943E+04	1.261	2.39	35.65	3.739E-3	-0.891
where	$k = A \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{E}{R \cdot T_C}\right)}$						

Table 2. Conductivities and specific heat for selected Hexcel materials in fully cured state

	Hexcel 3501-6 [14]	Hexcel 8552 [14]	Hexcel M18/1 (assumed)
Conductivity (W/mK)	0.167	0.128	0.150
Specific Heat (J/kgK)	1260	1025	1100

Fig. 12. Applied cure cycle and simulated temperatures contrasted with temperature signal of thermocouple TE 7

Table 3. Parameters of resin modulus development model

Description	Source	Quantity	Unit	Value
Young's modulus at low degrees of cure	Assumed	E_r^0	(Pa)	$4.2 \cdot 10^6$
Young's modulus for fully cured resin	[17]	E_r^∞	(Pa)	$4.2 \cdot 10^9$
Poisson's ratio for fully cured resin	[17]	ν_r^∞	(-)	0.40
Lower critical value for T^* , 160°C isothermal cure	T_{Cl}^* @ $\alpha=0.646$		(K)	-19.25
Lower critical value for T^* , 180°C isothermal cure	T_{Cl}^* @ $\alpha=0.706$		(K)	-25.11
Lower critical value for T^*	Linear fit for T_{Cl}^* 160°C and T_{Cl}^* 180°C	T_{Cl}^*	(K)	107.57
Variation of lower critical value with increase in temperature		T_{Cl}^*	(-)	-0.293
Upper critical value for T^*		T_{C2}^*	(K)	-9
Glass transition temperature of uncured resin	Measured and calibrated according to initial degree of cure α_0	T_{g0}	(K)	261.53
Variation of glass transition temperature with degree of cure	Calibrated to fit data sheet value for standard curing (196°C, [18])	a_{Tg}	(K)	235.67
Reference temperature	Set to ambient	T_0	(°C)	20
Secondary modulus variation with temperature	Assumed	a_{Er}	(1/K)	0

Table 4. Gathered fiber property data

Description	Source	Quantity	Unit	Value
Young's modulus, longitudinal	[20]	E_{1F}	(GPa)	227
Young's modulus, transverse	[20]	E_{2F}	(GPa)	17.25
Shear modulus,	[20]	G_{12F}	(GPa)	13.8
Shear modulus, transverse/transverse plain	[20]	G_{23F}	(GPa)	6.9
Poisson ratio, longitudinal/transverse plain	[20]	ν_{12F}	(-)	0.2
Poisson ratio, transverse/transverse plain	[20]	ν_{23F}	(-)	0.25
CTE, longitudinal direction	[6]	α_{1F}	($\mu\text{m}/\text{mK}$)	0.03
CTE, transverse direction	[6]	α_{2F}	($\mu\text{m}/\text{mK}$)	7.2
Density	[20]	ρ_F	(kg/m^3)	1790
Heat conductivity, longitudinal direction, at $T=0^\circ\text{C}$	[6]	$k_{2F,0}$	(W/mK)	7.69
Variation of heat conductivity in longitudinal direction with	[6]	$k_{2F,T}$	($\text{W}/\text{mK}^\circ\text{C}$)	$1.56 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Heat conductivity, transverse direction, at $T=0^\circ\text{C}$	[6]	$k_{2F,0}$	(W/mK)	2.40
Variation of heat conductivity in transverse direction with temperature	[6]	$k_{2F,T}$	($\text{W}/\text{mK}^\circ\text{C}$)	$5.07 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Specific heat capacity at $T=0^\circ\text{C}$	[6]	$C_{PF,0}$	(J/kgK)	750
Variation of specific heat capacity with temperature	[6]	$C_{PF,T}$	($\text{J}/\text{kgK}^\circ\text{C}$)	2.05

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